

OPTIMIZATION OF THE COMPOSITE CURE PROCESS ON THE BASIS OF THERMO-KINETIC MODEL

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Abstract

High performance composite structures produced by the processes at which the consolidation of the fibres and matrix is done at the same time as the component is shaped. Full curing schedule include a pre-warming for resin liquefaction, next apply of pressure to remove the gas bubbles, and finally consolidation of resin at elevated temperature to its full polymerization. The change in the state of the composite should be made as possible uniformly across the thick-walled products. The complexity of process control is due to unobservability of the rheological state of material in a closed volume of a mould. In this paper we propose a mathematical model of epoxy-based thick-walled composite structure curing. PDE system linking a kinetic equation of the resin cure with heat transfer equation, take into account a phase transition from liquid to gel and further to the solid state. On the basis of transient analysis of the developed model we optimize the temperature control law.

1 The Problems of Thermoset Composite Cure

The manufacturing processes for thermoset composites are subject to extensive research [1 - 3] and the number of models has been proposed for mould filling/consolidation and cure for several manufacturing methods. The purpose of these models is the optimization of the production process to ensure the specified properties of the material, to reducing the residual stress and shape distortions.

In an industrial process, it is economically advantageous to minimize the cure time [4] by increasing the cure temperature and providing a faster crosslinking reaction. But this can lead to significant loss of the composite product quality, which appears in the forms of large shape distortions and delaminations. In general, residual stresses and shape distortions will increase with increased cure

temperature [5]. Moreover, at some conditions in a thick-walled epoxy based composite pieces at high cure temperature the cracks in the resin can be observed due to cure shrinkage. To avoid this problem, instead of using a single step cure schedule, in the some cases gelled the resin at low temperature and slow increased the temperature by a linear ramp up to its maximal value [6].

We consider here the problem of optimizing the cure cycle on an example of a composite spar of the helicopter rotor blade. The technology of manufacturing of fiberglass reinforcement with epoxy resin matrix composite spar include the following phases: winding of a prepregged unidirectional glass-fiber tape on a steel mandrel; polymerization of a prepreg in a mould (see Fig. 1) within approximately 16 hours. After complete cure the mould is slowly cooled and opened, and the component released and removed from a mandrel. The quality of a ready piece is dependent on the sequence and magnitude of temperature and pressure actions.

The complexity of the spar quality assuring is due to liberation of considerable exothermal heat, and usually very poorly controlled because of inability monitoring of temperature and stress in the body spar inside the mold. The presented model of the epoxy based composites curing processes take into account the kinetics of the thermoset resin reactions, changing its phase state, thermal capacitance during cure, and heat transfer in the technological system. On the basis of this model we formulate and solve the problem of optimal temperature schedule for cure process. Using this model largely eliminates the effect of "unobservability" of high-strength composites technology and improves process control system, thereby providing improved quality and reliability of composite structures.

Fig. 1. Typical cross-section of a mold for composite spar cure

2 The Kinetic Model of Thermoset Resin Cure

The temperature schedule of a thermoset resin is determined by a triple diagram of temperature - time - state, which link the resin state during cure (liquid - gel - glass) with temperature and time of chemical reactions. Change the phase state of resin, which occurs in the form of an initial liquefaction and reducing the viscosity of the liquid transition to the gel-like state (gelation), and the subsequent transition to the solid state. It is important that, unlike crystalline materials all epoxy based polymers change its state at certain temperature range, and location of this range can be different at variation of thermal - temporal schedule for the same resin material. Therefore, accepted in the scientific literature and used herein the terms "gel transition", "glass transition" refers to a range of temperatures rather than to a strictly fixed temperature, as is the case in crystalline solids. Another feature of the thermoset cure reaction is the discharge of the exothermal heat, and the maximum of the exothermic heat can occur at single (one-step reaction) or more (two-stage reaction) temperatures. It is accepted that the amount of evolved heat during the exothermic reaction characterizes the degree of polymerization of thermoset resin. Quantitative assessment of the degree of cure (ie, conversion) is $\alpha \equiv Q(t)/Q_0$ ($\alpha \in [0;1]$), where $Q(t)$, Q_0 - an actual and the total heat during the polymerization of unit mass [7, 8].

Most common way to describing the cure process is the dependence of conversion rate on conversion, named as the kinetic curve, which give a visual representation of the polymerization kinetics. First quantitative description of the cure process given by the kinetic equation is applied by Kamal [7] for epoxy resin, and the generalized form of the kinetic equation for the cure reactions is presented in [1]. This generalized model has 9 constants, allowing it a good flexibility. The means for constructing a kinetic curves experimentally is the Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) method that implements the monitoring of thermal processes during polymerization.

For investigated epoxy resin we used a DSC scanning at the following temperature program: 1st and 2nd heating in a nitrogen atmosphere from 20 °C to 300 °C with heating rate 5, 10, 20 K / min; and cooling from 300 °C to 20 °C.

After numerical processing of DSC scans the dependencies $d\alpha(\alpha, T)/dt, C(\alpha, T)$ have been derived. On the basis of $d\alpha(\alpha, T)/dt$ dependence which is the two-modal kinetic curves (see Fig. 2), a new kinetic model and empirical dependence for heat capacity have been proposed

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \left[A_1 \cdot e^{\left(\frac{E_1}{RT}\right)} \cdot e^{-\frac{\alpha}{\alpha_i}} + A_2 \cdot e^{\left(\frac{E_2}{RT}\right)} \cdot \alpha^m \right] \cdot (1-\alpha)^n \quad (1)$$

$C_r = [C_f - (C_f - 1.15C_s) \cdot H(\alpha - \alpha_i, \delta\alpha)] \cdot (.8 + .2e^{-\alpha})$ (2) where C_f and C_s are the specific heats of uncured (liquid) and fully polymerized (solid) resin respectively; conversion α_i corresponding to the jump of heat capacity at phase transition, and the width of the jump in the smoothed Heaviside function H have defined by the empirical relationships

$$\alpha_i = .05 + .45 \tanh^2\left(\frac{dT/dt}{12}\right), \quad (3)$$

$$\delta\alpha = .1 + .4 \left[1 - \exp\left(\frac{dT/dt}{15}\right) \right]. \quad (4)$$

Eq. (2) describes the jump of the heat capacity at the transition, and "broadening" of this jump with increasing heating rate. Relation similar to Eq. (2) is used for the value of resin thermal conductivity. To do this, simply replace $k_r \rightarrow C_r$; $k_f \rightarrow C_f$; $k_s \rightarrow C_s$.

OPTIMIZATION OF THE COMPOSITE CURE PROCESS ON THE BASIS OF THERMO-KINETIC MODEL

Fig. 2. The kinetic curves calculated from Eq. (1)

The empirical dependencies (2) - (4) of the specific heat and thermal conductivity on the degree of cure for investigated epoxy resin are shown on a Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The dependencies of specific heat (top) and thermal conductivity (bottom) on the conversion at different heating rates

3 Model for Coupled Cure Kinetics and Heat Transfer in Epoxy Composite

Known attempts (e.g. [8]) to the analytical solving of the distributed resin transfer molding problem encountered significant mathematical difficulties. More efficient finite element (FEM) approach were used in [1, 3, 10] and others for solving problems related to the coupled thermo-kinetic processes at composites curing. This approach was used by us. The prototype for the problem formulation was the curing of composite spar for helicopter rotor blades in mold, which has described above. After pre-heating and dilution of resin creates pressure, clamping prepreg to the forming surfaces. The excess resin can be freely moved away the mold. Thus, the front of polymerized material, moving from the external hot surfaces, is not constrained by a liquid phase. Consideration of the finished product cooling and formation of the residual thermal stress is beyond the scope of the presented work, and not discussed below. Problem is formulated for an arbitrary subdomain of a composite body, heated on one side and exchanged heat with a steel mandrel.

Here's the full problem statement.

- The heat transfer equation

$$\rho_c C_c \partial T / \partial t + \nabla(-k_c \nabla T) = Q_{exo} \quad (5)$$

- the kinetics equation (1) for conversion $\alpha(\mathbf{r}, T, t)$ which is a function of space coordinates, temperature, and time;

- composite density

$$\rho_c = \rho_f v_f + \rho_r (1 - v_f) \quad (6)$$

- the heat transfer coefficient of composite

$$k_c = k_r \cdot \frac{(1 + v_{fb}) \cdot k_{fb} + (1 - v_{fb}) \cdot k_r}{(1 - v_{fb}) \cdot k_{fb} + (1 + v_{fb}) \cdot k_r}, \quad (7)$$

where actual value of the resin matrix heat transfer coefficient k_r is defined by a function of conversion

$$k_r = [k_f - (k_f - 1.145k_s) \cdot H(\alpha - \alpha_i, \delta\alpha)] \cdot (8 + .2e^{-\alpha}), \quad (8)$$

- the specific thermal capacity of composite

$$C_c = C_{fb} v_{fb} + C_r (1 - v_{fb}) \quad (9)$$

where C_r is defined by Eqs. (2) - (4);

- an intensity of the internal heat sources

$$Q_{exo} = Q_{tot} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \quad (10)$$

In the above equations index fr indicates the reinforcing fibers, and the index r - resin matrix.

It is convenient in the real world cases to use preliminary created CAD models as is presented on the Fig. 4. Because of approximately symmetrical all cross sections of the cured spar it is appropriate to consider only half of structure. Conversion from *.x_t CAD format to the FEM format were performed by Comsol Multiphysics built-in converter (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. CAD model of the cured spar

Fig. 5. FEM model of the molded spar.
From top to bottom: one half of the spar;
spar in the mold; model after FEM meshing

Eqs (1-4) and (6-10) are active in the spar body only, and heat transfer equation (5) is active everywhere. All boundary conditions depend on the cured piece and mold geometry and also on the scheme of controlled heating. On the cut and end surfaces the insulation/symmetry boundary conditions have been set

$$-\mathbf{n} \cdot (-k \nabla T) = 0; \quad -\mathbf{n} \cdot (-\nabla \alpha) = 0, \quad (11)$$

at the interfaces between metal and cured composite used continuity boundary conditions

$$-\mathbf{n}_s \cdot (-k_c \nabla T) - \mathbf{n}_m \cdot (-k_m \nabla T) = 0 \quad (12)$$

where lower indices indicates s – composite spar, m – metallic bold and mandrel. On the heated sides surfaces the temperature is maintained according to some law $T_{heat}(t)$.

The coupled equations (1) - (12) with material parameters obtained from DSC data has been numerically implemented in the Heat Transfer and PDE (partial differential equation) modules included into Comsol Multiphysics FEM software, and solved inside the modeling domain (usually with zero initial conditions) by. At each integration step all local values of specific heat, thermal conductivity, and the intensity of heat sources inside the composite domain were recalculated according to their conversion dependencies.

The preliminary numerical simulations have revealed a strong dependence of conversion temporal behavior on the spar walls thickness. In order to avoid formation the internal peel and cavities due to overgrowth heating rate, and also an incomplete polymerization product in the area of thickening, a problem of optimal heating control was formulated and solved using the developed FEM model.

4 Model Based Optimization of the Temperature Schedule

In the real world technology the heating control is implemented by a set of electrical heaters and thermocouples installed into the body of mold. Hence, a local temperature in the mold points is the monitored parameter which is regulated by a heat flux from electric heaters. Because of slow heating and high-speed performance of controller it most convenient to set the controlled temperature on the heated boundaries.

OPTIMIZATION OF THE COMPOSITE CURE PROCESS ON THE BASIS OF THERMO-KINETIC MODEL

We have chosen the cost function as the maximum spreading of conversion gradient inside the cured spar

$$J = \max_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla \alpha|_{t_0} \right) \quad (13)$$

at nonlinear integral constraints

$$\alpha_1 \leq \langle \alpha \rangle_{t_0} \leq \alpha_2 \quad (14)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \alpha \rangle &\equiv \int_{\Omega} \alpha(\mathbf{r}, T, t) d\omega, \\ \langle \nabla \alpha \rangle &\equiv \int_{\Omega} |\nabla \alpha(\mathbf{r}, T, t)| d\omega \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The cost function is minimized by varying the temperature on the heated boundary. Boundary values α_1, α_2 in the expression (14) were adopted different for each stage of the process. Thus, at stage of liquefaction $\alpha_1 = 0.15, \alpha_2 = 0.25$, and at final stage of curing $\alpha_1 = 0.97, \alpha_2 = 1$. The optimal form of the temperature growth on the heated surface was found by trial and error. This is the sum of time-dependent hyperbolic tangent and exponential. At first stage (liquefaction) and at second stage (solidification) of cure four numerical parameters of these functions were determined by a built-in Nelder-Mead optimization algorithm. Thus, the problem solving has divided by two stages. And solution obtained on the first stage of optimization was used as initial condition for the second stage. At each step the optimization algorithm performed a transient analysis of the cure process till time t_0 , which can be defined from production and material properties requirements.

Optimized temperature variation law $T_{heat}^{opt}(t)$ is presented on a Fig. 6, where points of resin complete liquefaction (applying of pressure) and completion of heating were depicted. Graphs of averaged conversion and averaged conversion's gradient, presented on a Fig. 7, show that used control heating algorithm ensures a sufficiently homogeneous state of the material at the stage liquefaction (time close to 3 hours), as well as a smooth transition to the solid state in 20 hours after the molding.

At each time of simulation the spatial distribution of temperature, conversion, exothermal heat, and heat fluxes can be monitored as one can see on the Fig.8, where slice plot for conversion is presented.

Fig. 6. Optimized control law of heating temperature

Fig. 7. Time charts of averaged conversion (top) and averaged gradient of conversion (bottom) when optimized temperature control is applied

Fig. 8. Spatial conversion distribution into the cured spar body at time of resin complete liquefaction

Conclusion

The model of spatially distributed curing process of epoxy-based matrix polymeric composite was developed and implemented using the finite element method. This mathematical model is a system of coupled partial differential equations: heat transfer equation with spatially distributed exothermal heat source and kinetic equation for conversion (degree of cure) in the cured resin. At time of simulation the kinetic equation modify the fields of conversion, thermal conductivity, and heat capacitance of composite. To correctly reconstruct a kinetic equation and to accounting a phase transition from liquid to gel and further to the solid state we used the DSC and DMA experimental data.

The geometry of modeled process can be imported from the CAD model and converted to a suitable finite element representation. Developed model allowed us to determine the critical factors controlled the quality parameters of the composite material, and appoint needed technological conditions.

On the basis of model for the composite cure we formulated and solved a minimization problem with objective as the maximum spreading of conversion gradient inside the cured spar to optimize the heating schedule and to forming thick-walled composite spar with homogenous structure and minimal thermal stresses, leading to piece distortion.

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